

Research Article

Post-Pandemic Socio-Emotional Skills Vis-a-Vis Quality of Learning of Senior High School Learners in the Division of Biñan City: Basis for Crafting Programs and Learning Strategies

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Article History	Abstract
<p>Received: April 18, 2026 Accepted: May 10, 2026 Published: May 18, 2026</p>	<p>Mixed quantitative and qualitative research design was used in this study in determining the post-pandemic socio-emotional skills and the quality of learning of senior high school students, which were affected by the COVID-19 pandemic that impacted the Philippine education system posing extraordinarily disturbing challenges. Aligned with DepEd's Learning Recovery Plan (LRP) Framework, this research aimed to craft programs and learning strategy plans to facilitate learning recovery processes. SHS students, teachers, and guidance advocates from the Division of Biñan City served as research respondents and participants. Findings showed that learners' post-pandemic level of socio-emotional skills was "highly competent". Working collaboratively with others and cooperating in class rather than doing tasks alone dominated preferences among social skills, while accepting differences in beliefs, values, and sexual preferences rather than imposing theirs on others marked the highest preference among the emotional skills. The post-pandemic quality of learning was "above average". Strong motivation to learn with others characterizes the improved post-pandemic quality of learning. Using Pearson r correlation coefficient, a negative linear correlation but significant relationship between the social skills and quality of learning was found; similarly, a strong positive linear correlation and significant relationship between emotional skills and quality of learning, and a weak positive correlation and significant relationship between the socio-emotional skills and quality of learning were also found. In-person classes were preferred as effective learning modality in developing socio-emotional skills and consequently improving the quality of learning. Guidance programs on socio-emotional skills development and learning strategies on real-life situations were recommended.</p> <p>Keywords: Post-Pandemic Socio-Emotional Skills, Quality of Learning, Learning Recovery Plan, Learning Modalities.</p>

Introduction

Learning Recovery Plan (LCP) is the framework developed by DepEd as it announced the resumption of in-person classes in all basic education schools. The framework that DepEd has developed necessitated schools to devise plans on how to address the learning gaps due to the pandemic-related disruptions. Perceptions on the effectiveness of various learning modalities during the pandemic have surfaced, thus necessitating DepEd and other stakeholders to look for urgent possible means and ways to evaluate learning and to do the most appropriate interventions to address the gaps in the teaching-learning process.

DepEd Order No. 13, s. 2023 or the adoption of the National Learning Recovery Program (NLRP) in the Department of Education reiterated its commitment to address the learning loss heightened by school closures and disruption during the COVID-19 pandemic. Anchored on the MATATAG curriculum, DepEd adopts the

NLRP to strengthen the learning recovery and continuity plan of the department, improve numeracy and literacy, and accelerate the achievement of the education targets, all these are stipulated in the same department order.

The effects of the pandemic were massive and gigantic and that it did not only affect the process of learning per se, but the dispositions of the learners as well. Soft skills that should have been developed, if not due to the shift in learning modalities brought about by the pandemic, were perceived to be the missing piece in the distance learning modalities. Tria (2020), in his article, the COVID-19 pandemic through the lens of education in the Philippines: the new normal, stated that the pandemic with its extraordinary challenges disturbed the educational processes. This necessitated the policy makers in the education sector to plan and implement new normal procedures. One of those areas that had been considered in the implementation of the new normal in education was the issue of the development of learners' socio-emotional skills which evidently becomes limited due to the absence of other significant individuals like physical connection with teachers and peers. According to George *et al.*, (2021), due to the COVID-19 pandemic, lack of in-person schooling and increased stress can affect neurodevelopment, mental health, and later life outcomes among students. They mentioned those learners who come from low socio-economic status households. Studies show that this physical connection during the learning process is greatly significant.

Baafi (2020) discovered that the students in senior high schools with a pleasant physical environment perform better than those where the learning environment is not conducive. His study confirmed the significance of the school physical environment implying therefore that learning modalities other than in-person were not preferable. There were studies that show the limited to zero interactions of parents with adult learners like the senior high school learners. To this effect, it could be predicted that the distance learning for lower key stages in the department might be effective because parents and/or significant adults are more engaged and involved in the learning process, serving as the para-teachers of the young learners; but controversies on its effectiveness for higher key stages are likewise considered. Some may argue that senior high school learners are independent learners, thus for its argument's sake, distance learning could also be effective among them. In a comparative analysis, Cano (2022) found out that the traditional face-to-face and online distance learning modality could improve learners' academic performance. Therefore, although there were a good number of studies on the effect of pandemic to learners' school performance, the argument, nevertheless, still exists as to whether learners really develop holistic learning which includes factors on the development of socio emotional skills.

With the new DepEd administration headed by no less than the Vice President of the Philippines, Honorable Education Secretary Sarah Duterte, the department was also embarking on various initiatives to set the new directions of the agency and stakeholders in resolving basic education challenges through DepEd MATATAG agenda. Every school to this effect was embarking on specific directions and initiatives, through its own LRCP, to contextually respond to the department's challenges such as, first, making the curriculum relevant to produce competent and job-ready, active and responsible citizens; second, taking steps to accelerate delivery of basic education facilities and services; third, taking good care of learners by promoting learner well-being, inclusive education, and a positive learning environment; and fourth, giving support to teachers to teach better. This current research sought to figure out the post-pandemic socio-emotional skills and the quality of learning of senior high school students, and to determine whether there is a significant relationship between the post-pandemic socio-emotional skills and the quality of learning of SHS learners in the Division of Biñan City.

A list of recommendations was enumerated as basis for crafting programs and learning strategies. All the abovementioned directions and initiatives of the department can be addressed. First, the curriculum can be contextualized to address the gaps between the post pandemic socio-emotional skills and the quality of learning of senior high school learners. Consequently, this would produce competent and job-ready, active, and responsible citizens. Second, the school's facilities and services could be reviewed to align with the needs of the learners. Third, learners' well-being will be directly addressed by this study. Lastly, with the main output, that is, a crafted guidance program and learning strategy, the quality of teaching-learning process could be enhanced.

It is undeniable that all learners were affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. Experts revealed that learning gaps in all key learning stages were evident. The critical four components of the MATATAG agenda, as stipulated in DepEd Order No. 13, s. 2023, serve as the guide of the subprograms under the National Learning Recovery Plan (NLRP) which include: NLC or National Learning Camp, NRP or National Reading Program, NMP or National Mathematics Program, NSTP or National Science and Technology Program, and other programs that support

learning recovery efforts. All these programs and initiatives were geared toward learning recovery, there was doubt about it, however, as a senior high school teacher and guidance advocate for four years, the researcher perceived the need to determine how the quality of learning of the senior high school learners in the Division of Biñan City was affected by their socio-emotional skills which are necessary tools to concretely respond to the challenges. This was anchored on the premise that it was not only the learning process per se that was affected by the COVID-19 pandemic but also the mental, emotional, social, economic, and other aspects of a particular learner were also affected. Therefore, this present study sought to figure out the significant relationship between the socio-economic skills and the quality of learning of SHS learners, which eventually led to the development of guidance programs and learning strategy plans that would address their learning needs.

This present study would promote advocacy to spread awareness that the teaching-learning process does not only focus on intellectual enlightenment but also a pursuit for holistic personal development that includes social and emotional aspects of the learners. The results of this study would be disseminated in various forms such as advocacy campaigns using social media platforms, printed information campaign promoting the importance of socio-emotional enhancement in education, and through other forms. With school-based training for teachers, this advocacy could also be disseminated like focused-group discussions (FGD), school learning action cell (SLAC), and district or division research conferences.

Material and Methods

The type of research design or methodology used in this study was mixed descriptive quantitative and qualitative. The descriptive quantitative method was used to obtain quantifiable data that involved numeric and statistical explanations using the validated researcher-made research questionnaire, while the descriptive qualitative method was used to obtain data that were described in detail using research tool like interview (Cornell *et al.*, 2014). The former's data were gathered, analyzed and interpreted using the most appropriate statistical tools, while the latter's data were gathered, analyzed and interpreted using thematic approach. Likert scale in determining the level of socio-emotional skills and the quality of learning of senior high school learners was utilized.

The respondents and participants of this study were public SHS learners, teachers and guidance advocates in the public Senior High School providers in the Division of Biñan City for the school year 2023-2024 such as: Biñan City Senior High School – Sto. Tomas Campus (Barangay Sto. Tomas), Biñan City Senior High School – San Antonio Campus (Barangay San Antonio), Biñan City Senior High School – Timbao Campus (Barangay Timbao), Biñan Integrated National High School (Barangay Sto. Domingo), Biñan City Senior High School – West Campus (Barangay Langkiwa), and St. Francis Integrated National High School (Barangay San Francisco).

Learners as the main subjects of the study were the most appropriate sources of information as they were those who directly experienced the effects of pandemic in their socio-emotional skills, particularly on their pursuit of knowledge and skills. The teachers as directly in-charge and facilitators of learners in the teaching-learning process were the most reliable sources of information, particularly in the indicators of learners' performance. Lastly, the guidance advocates who were tasked to perform differentiated strategies to address the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic to senior high school learners were equally sources of data that determine the socio-emotional skills of the learners. These are the reasons why they were considered as significant research respondents and participants.

The respondents and participants in this study were public SHS learners enrolled in public SHS providers in the Division of Biñan City for the school year 2023-2024. They were selected using purposive random sampling to give them equal chances of being part of this study. If they were enrolled in any of public SHS providers in the Division of Biñan City, they would be included in the study. Further, they were considered as research respondents and participants since they experienced the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic in the development of their socio-emotional skills. Another set of participants were public SHS teachers and guidance advocates. The teacher-participants were purposively selected regardless of subjects they handled because the effects of the pandemic in the socio emotional skills development of the learners in terms of its relationship with subject or discipline was not under investigation in this present study. Therefore, every teacher in senior high school in the Division of Biñan City had equal opportunity to take part in this study. As mentioned above, guidance advocates had significant roles in contributing to the development of this study.

As to the number of participants per public SHS providers were obtained, the researcher utilized purposive random sampling technique in the selection of learners and teachers/guidance advocate participants to

answer quantitative questions. Noor and Golzar (2022) described this sampling as a widely utilized sampling method in quantitative studies with survey questionnaire. With these all learners, teachers, and guidance advocates in the target schools of this study had equal chances to be selected as participants. Purposive sampling was used to select the respondents for interviews. This type of sampling refers to a deliberate collection of respondents based on their ability to expound on the topic under investigation.

The main instrument used in this study was survey questionnaires. It was made by the researcher and was validated by experts in the Department of Education – SDO Biñan City. They were requested since their expertise was found related to this study. The researcher asked permission to conduct interviews to clarify the data gathered from randomly selected respondents.

The approval of the Schools Division Superintendent for the data collection was also sought. A Division Memorandum stating the approved research proposal as well as the Regional Memorandum stating the BERF approval of this research were presented to the respective Public Schools District Supervisors of districts where public SHS providers were located. Upon obtaining their approval and endorsement, coordination through formal letter was handed over to respective school heads of the six (6) public senior high school providers in the Division of Biñan City.

Through the letter of request to the school heads, the researcher arranged the schedules for data gathering through survey questionnaires, and another schedule, for the conduct of interviews. Focused Group Discussion of FGD was conducted to personally interact with the research participants and to clarify issues or concerns related to survey questionnaire and interview guide questions.

To gather data, various modalities were considered such as: first, using face-to-face interviews, with keen consideration of research participants’ privacy being respected; second, using pencil and paper instrument; third by answering Google Form to give the research participants options in answering the interview questions on time that is very convenient to them, but no one among them accessed the Google Form link because they preferred the two other modalities.

Results and Discussion

The result of this study was based on the analysis, presentation and interpretation of the data gathered. There were two phases in the analysis, presentation and interpretation. The first part was based on the results of the questionnaire focusing on the quantitative analysis of data, and the second part was based on the results of the interview and focus group discussions focusing on the qualitative analysis of data.

Table 1. Student respondents’ profile.

Gender			Grade level		
Male	Female	Total	Grade 11	Grade 12	Total
71	72	143	45	98	164
49.65%	50.35%	100.00%	31.47%	68.53%	100.00%

Table 1 shows that female student-respondents were just one higher than male student-respondents. There were 71 or 49.65% male respondents, while there were 72 or 50.35% female respondents. In terms of grade levels, most of them came from grade 12 with 98 or 68.53% respondents, while only 45 or 31.47% came from grade 11. Most of the respondents was female and belonged to grade 12 level.

Table 2. Teacher/guidance advocate respondents’ profile.

Position			Work experience				
Teacher	Guidance advocate	Total	0-3	4-5	6-10	Above 10	Total
22	4	26	5	6	7	8	26
84.62%	15.38%	100.00%	19.23%	23.08%	26.92%	30.77%	100.00%

Table 2 shows that there were more teacher-respondents than guidance advocate-respondents. There were only 4 or 15.38% of guidance advocate respondents, while there were 22 or 84.62% teacher respondents. In terms of work experience, most of them have been serving their profession for more than 10 years with 8 or 30.77%, followed by respondents who have been serving 6-10 years with 7 or 26.92%, next, by those who have been serving for 4-5 years with 6 or 23.08%, while there were only 5 or 19.23% have been serving their profession from 0-3 years. Most of the respondents was teachers, and had above ten (10) work experience, while the least had only zero to three (0-3) years work experience.

Table 3. SHS learners’ post-pandemic level of socio-emotional skills as assessed by students, teachers and guidance advocate respondents.

SHS learners’ post-pandemic level of socio-emotional skills	Groups	Weighted mean	Verbal interpretation
1. Social skills			
1.1 Learners show comfort in dealing with all kinds of acquaintances such as teachers, school authorities, and peers rather than being aloof most of the time/I am comfortable in dealing with all kinds of acquaintances such as teachers, school authorities, and peers rather than being aloof most of the time.	Student	3.21	Highly competent
	Teacher/GA	3.12	Highly competent
	Overall	3.17	Highly competent
1.2 Learners collaboratively work with other students in completing their tasks and cooperate in class activities rather than doing their tasks alone / I collaboratively work with other students in completing my tasks and cooperating in class activities rather than doing my tasks alone.	Student	3.41	Highly competent
	Teacher/GA	3.29	Highly competent
	Overall	3.35	Highly competent
1.3 Learners approach their peers and teachers for clarifications on a given task rather than doing it based on their personal understanding/I approach my peers and my teachers for clarifications on a given task rather than doing it based on my personal understanding.	Student	3.34	Highly competent
	Teacher/GA	3.34	Highly competent
	Overall	3.34	Highly competent
1.4 Learners consider other’s feelings and ideas before they say words and perform an act rather than focusing on their own feelings and perspectives / I consider other’s feelings and ideas before I say words and perform an act rather than focusing on my own feelings and perspectives.	Student	3.12	Highly competent
	Teacher/GA	3.44	Highly competent
	Overall	3.28	Highly competent
1.5 Learners avoid teasing peers and accept corrective feedback from teachers and authorities rather than being self-centered/I avoid teasing peers and accept corrective feedback from teachers and authorities rather than being self-centered.	Student	3.12	Highly competent
	Teacher/GA	3.43	Highly competent
	Overall	3.28	Highly competent
2. Emotional skills			
2.1 Learners display self-confidence when assigned to perform rather than avoiding any participation in any performance tasks/I display self-confidence when assigned to perform rather than avoiding any participation in any performance tasks.	Student	3.18	Highly competent
	Teacher/GA	3.17	Highly competent
	Overall	3.18	Highly competent
2.2 Learners accept differences in beliefs, values, and sexual preferences rather than imposing theirs on others/I accept differences in beliefs, values, and sexual preferences rather than imposing mine on others.	Student	3.42	Highly competent
	Teacher/GA	3.59	Highly competent
	Overall	3.50	Highly competent
2.3 Learners cope with academic challenges rather than deviating and/or quitting their tasks / I cope with academic challenges rather than deviating and/or quitting my tasks.	Student	3.24	Highly competent
	Teacher/GA	3.38	Highly competent
	Overall	3.31	Highly competent

Table 3 shows the SHS learners’ post-pandemic level of socio-emotional skills as assessed by students, teachers and guidance advocate respondents. Five items were assessed under social skills and three items under emotional skills. The question was: “What is the level of socio-emotional skills of the SHS learners as perceived by the students and teachers/guidance advocates’ respondents?” From the data, the following results were obtained and shown in Table 3.

In terms of social skills, item 1.2 “Learners collaboratively work with other students in completing their tasks and cooperate in class activities rather than doing their tasks alone” got the highest overall weighted mean of 3.35; the students got a weighted mean of 3.41; while the teachers/guidance advocates, 3.29; thus the perception on the SHS learners’ post-pandemic level of social skills of this item was interpreted as “highly competent”.

It was followed by item 1.3 “Learners approach their peers and teachers for clarifications on a given task rather than doing it based on their personal understanding”, with an overall weighted mean of 3.34; where both groups rated this item as 3.34 equally.

Items 1.4 “Learners consider other’s feelings and ideas before they say words and perform an act rather than focusing on their own feelings and perspectives” and 1.5 “Learners avoid teasing peers and accept corrective feedback from teachers and authorities rather than being self-centered”, were ranked 3rd with overall weighted mean of 3.28.

Lastly, item 1.1 “Learners show comfort in dealing with all kinds of acquaintances such as teachers, school authorities, and peers rather than being aloof most of the time” obtained the lowest overall weighted mean of 3.17 where students got 3.21, while teachers/guidance advocates got 3.12, although it was still interpreted that the perception on the SHS learners’ post-pandemic level of social skills of this item was interpreted as “highly competent”. It was also shown that while learners preferred to collaboratively work with other students in completing their tasks than doing them alone, it was also evident that they considered showing comfort in dealing with all kinds of acquaintances such as teachers, school authorities, and peers, rather than being alone aloof most of the time, as their least preferences among the indicators of social skills competence.

This result affirmed Zhao (2022), who investigated teacher-student relationships in physical education activities in the context of inter-subjectivity. In his study, Zhao claimed that the effectiveness of physical education on the campus, including the cultivation of students’ moral character, is affected by the quality of communication between teachers and students. Likewise, Joonggeun Oh (2021), who investigated teacher student relationship and class flow in physical education class, the mediating effect of emotion regulation claimed that students reduced problematic behavior, increased academic motivation, achievement, and emotion regulation were affected by positive teacher-student relationships. Another study revealed that positive teacher-student relationship enhances the students’ positive attitude towards physical education classes (Sahin, 2019). To determine whether teacher-student rapport could favorably influence students’ academic behaviors, Zhou (2021) conducted a study which aimed to explain this phenomenon. It was found out that indeed it has positive consequences for students’ academic engagement in practical instruction classrooms. This implies that physical connections between teachers and learners can affect academic performance and eventually the socio-emotional skills of the learners to that effect. All these studies, including this present study, therefore conveyed that collaboration with peers and teachers in doing tasks improved one’s social skills and they would become “highly competent”.

In terms of emotional skills, item 2.2 “Learners accept differences in beliefs, values, and sexual preferences rather than imposing theirs on others” obtained the highest overall weighted mean of 3.50.

It was followed by item 2.3 “Learners cope with academic challenges rather than deviating and/or quitting their tasks” with an overall weighted mean of 3.31; where students’ rating of 3.24 was lower than the rating of teachers/guidance advocates which was 3.38.

Item 2.1 “Learners display self-confidence when assigned to perform rather than avoiding any participation in any performance tasks”, on the other hand got the lowest overall weighted mean of 3.18 where students got 3.18 and teachers /guidance advocates got 3.17.

The results showed that the emotional skills were “highly competent”, specifically in terms of accepting their differences in terms of beliefs, values, and sexual preferences. Accepting such differences than imposing theirs on others was manifested. Nevertheless, displaying self-confidence to perform than avoiding participation was the lowest which was an indicator that this emotional skill must be addressed in school now that the resumption of face-to-face classes has been implemented. The study conducted by Hachem *et al.*, (2022) on social and emotional variables as predictors of students perceived cognitive competence and academic performance to determine whether socio-emotional skills are important in learning and development, was affirmed in this present study. The result showed that while collaborative work is important, it was likewise

important to accept everyone’s diverse perspectives. Like Hachem *et al.*, it was also proven in this study that social and emotional variables have a direct impact on students’ competence and academic performance. Based on the responses by students and teachers/guidance advocates, it was found out that indeed learning is a highly social process, and as such we could prioritize investing into the enhancement of socio emotional skills among our learners. This could be more effective if the primary focus is on creating positive and supportive environments. This was supported by the findings of the studies conducted by Sahin (2019), Joonggeun (2021), Zhao (2022), and Hachem *et al.*, (2022) which showed that indeed learning is a highly social process, and as such we could prioritize investing into the enhancement of socio emotional skills among our learners. This could be more effective if the primary focus is on creating positive and supportive environments.

Table 4. Description of the post-pandemic quality of learning of SHS students based on their performance during the resumption of in-person classes as assessed by students and teachers/guidance advocate respondents.

Indicators of quality of learning	Groups	Weighted mean	Verbal interpretation
1. Learners display strong motivation to learn with others/I display strong motivation to learn with others.	Student	3.30	Above average
	Teacher/GA	3.53	Above average
	Overall	3.42	Above average
2. Learners engage into group activities inside and outside the classroom/I engage into group activities inside and outside the classroom.	Student	3.44	Above average
	Teacher/GA	3.37	Above average
	Overall	3.40	Above average
3. Learners submit their outputs more efficiently and effectively/I submit my outputs more efficiently and effectively.	Student	3.03	Above average
	Teacher/GA	3.44	Above average
	Overall	3.24	Above average
4. Learners get higher scores in written works and quizzes/I get higher scores in written works and quizzes.	Student	3.00	Above average
	Teacher/GA	3.09	Above average
	Overall	3.04	Above average
5. Learners improve their scores (MPS) in periodical tests/I improve my scores in periodical tests.	Student	3.12	Above average
	Teacher/GA	3.23	Above average
	Overall	3.17	Above average
6. Learners attend class regularly (attendance is improved)/I attend class regularly (my attendance is improved).	Student	3.24	Above average
	Teacher/GA	3.57	Above average
	Overall	3.41	Above average
7. Learners come to classes on time (punctuality is improved)/I come to classes on time (my punctuality is improved).	Student	3.03	Above average
	Teacher/GA	3.33	Above average
	Overall	3.18	Above average
8. Learners’ grades are improved / my grades are improved.	Student	3.21	Above average
	Teacher/GA	3.41	Above average
	Overall	3.31	Above average
9. Learners show a remarkable level of interest in education/I show remarkable level of interest in education.	Student	3.24	Above average
	Teacher/GA	3.31	Above average
	Overall	3.27	Above average
10. Learners’ proficiency level is improved/my proficiency level is improved (my grades in all subjects are improved).	Student	3.21	Above average
	Teacher/GA	3.26	Above average
	Overall	3.24	Above average
11. Learners’ drop-out rate decreased/I do not consider dropping out.	Student	3.15	Above average
	Teacher/GA	3.59	Above average
	Overall	3.37	Above average
12. Learners’ promotion rate increased/my interest in getting promoted is improved.	Student	3.39	Above average
	Teacher/GA	3.41	Above average
	Overall	3.40	Above average

Table 4 shows the description of the post pandemic quality of learning of SHS students based on their performance during the resumption of in-person classes as assessed by students and teachers/guidance advocate respondents. Twelve items were assessed under this area where the respondents were asked: “How do the respondents describe the post-pandemic quality of learning of SHS students based on their performance during the resumption of in-person classes?” From the data the following results were obtained and shown in Table 4.

Item 1 “Learners display strong motivation to learn with others” had the highest overall weighted mean of 3.42; the students got a weighted mean of 3.30; while the teachers/guidance advocates, 3.53; thus, the description of the post pandemic quality of learning of SHS students based on their performance during the resumption of in-person as assessed by students and teachers/guidance advocate respondents of this item was interpreted as “above average”.

It was followed by item 6 “Learners attend class regularly (attendance is improved)” with an overall weighted mean of 3.41 where students obtained 3.24 weighted mean which was lower than teachers/guidance advocates’ which was 3.57.

Third in rank were items 2 “Learners engage into group activities inside and outside the classroom” and 12 “Learners’ promotion rate increased” with an overall weighted mean of 3.40. In item 2, the ratings of students which was 3.44 was higher than teachers/guidance advocates which was only 3.37; while in item 12, the ratings of both groups were almost the same with students weighted mean of 3.39 and with teachers/guidance advocates’ rating of 3.41.

Item 11 “Learners’ drop-out rate decreased” was ranked 4th with an overall weighted mean of 3.37, where students obtained 3.15 weighted mean against the weighted mean of teachers/guidance advocates which was 3.59.

Next in rank was item 8 “Learners’ grades are improved” with an overall weighted mean of 3.31; students’ rating of 3.21 was lower than 3.41 of teachers/guidance advocates’ rating. Item 9 “Learners show a remarkable level of interest in education” was next with an overall weighted mean of 3.27; where students’ rating of 3.24 was lower than 3.31 of teachers/guidance advocates.

Items 3 “Learners submit their outputs more efficiently and effectively” and item 10 “Learners’ proficiency level is improved” were equal with 3.24 overall weighted mean. Item, 7 “Learners come to classes on time (punctuality is improved)” was ranked 10th with an overall weighted mean of 3.18, where students’ rating was 3.03 while teachers/guidance advocates’ rating was 3.33. Ranked 11th was item 5 “Learners improve their scores (MPS) in periodical tests” with an overall weighted mean of 3.17; where students scored 3.12, while teachers/guidance advocates score 3.23.

Item 4 “Learners get higher scores in written works and quizzes” obtained the lowest overall weighted mean of 3.04 where students got 3.00, while teachers/guidance advocates got 3.09, although it was still interpreted that the description of the post pandemic quality of learning of SHS students based on their performance during the resumption of in-person of this item was “above average”.

Results showed that the level of post-pandemic quality of learning of SHS learners in the Division of Binan City was 3.29 or “above average”. Based on this result, the following studies were confirmed: Joonggeun Oh (2021) and Zhao (2022), both claimed that positive teachers-students connections resulted in increased academic performance as well as moral dispositions of learners. Sahin (2019) and Zhou (2021) conducted studies which aimed to explain this phenomenon. They found out that indeed it has positive consequences for students’ academic engagement in practical instruction classrooms. This implies that physical connections between teachers and learners can affect academic performance and eventually the socio-emotional skills of the learners to that effect. Lastly, Portela-Pino *et al.*, (2021), Burney (2022) and Hachem *et al.*, (2022) claimed that socio emotional skills seemed to have influenced the academic performance of students.

Table 5. Significant relationship between the socio-emotional skills and the quality of learning of SHS students based on their performance during the resumption of in-person classes as perceived by teachers/guidance advocates and students.

SHS learners’ post-pandemic skills and their quality of learning	Groups	WM	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Social skills	Students	3.34	-0.3624	.00001	Reject H ₀	Significant
	Teachers/GA	3.25				
Emotional skills	Students	3.34	0.9618	.00001	Reject H ₀	Significant
	Teachers/GA	3.25				
Quality of learning	Students	3.38	0.3555	.000013	Reject H ₀	Significant
	Teachers/GA	3.20				

Table 5 shows three variables such as social skills, emotional skills, and quality of learning. In terms of the post-pandemic social skills, the weighted mean of students with 3.34 is higher than the weighted mean obtained by the teachers and guidance advocates which is 3.25. Since the computed p-value is .00001 with a Pearson r value of -0.3624 is less than the standard level of significance which is 0.05, therefore the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the post-pandemic social skills and the post-pandemic quality of learning of SHS students based on their performance during the resumption of in-person classes as perceived by teachers/guidance advocates and students, was rejected. Although, there existed a negative correlation, it was still concluded that there was significant relationship between the post-pandemic social skills and the quality of learning of SHS students based on their performance during the resumption of in-person classes as perceived by teachers and students. This affirmed that results of the studies conducted by Portela-Pino *et al.*, (2021), Burney (2022) and Hachem *et al.*, (2022) who claimed that socio-emotional skills seem to have influenced the academic performance of students.

In terms of the post-pandemic emotional skills, the weighted mean of students with 3.34 is higher than the weighted mean obtained by the teachers and guidance advocates which is 3.25. Since the computed p-value is .0001 with a Pearson r value of 0.9618 is less than the standard level of significance which is 0.05, therefore the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the post-pandemic emotional skills and the post-pandemic quality of learning of SHS students based on their performance during the resumption of in-person classes as assessed by students and teachers/guidance advocates, was rejected. There was strong positive correlation, and there was significant relationship between the emotional skills and the quality of learning of SHS students based on their performance during the resumption of in-person classes as perceived by teachers and students. This result likewise affirmed the studies conducted by Portela-Pino *et al.*, (2021), Burney (2022) and Hachem *et al.*, (2022) who claimed that socio-emotional skills seem to have influenced the academic performance of students.

In terms of post-pandemic quality of learning, the weighted mean of students with 3.38 is higher than the weighted mean obtained by the teachers and guidance advocates which is 3.20. Since the computed p-value is .000013 with a Pearson r value of 0.3555 is less than the standard level of significance which is 0.05, therefore the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the post-pandemic socio-emotional skills and the quality of learning of SHS students based on their performance during the resumption of in-person classes as perceived by teachers/guidance advocates and students, was rejected. Although, there was weak positive linear correlation, and there was still significant relationship between the socio-emotional skills and the quality of learning of SHS students based on their performance during the resumption of in-person classes as perceived by teachers and students. This affirmed the study which aimed to determine whether teacher-student rapport could favorably influence students' academic behaviors which was conducted by Zhou (2021) who aimed to explain this phenomenon. It was found out that indeed it had positive consequences for students' academic engagement in practical instruction classrooms. This implied that physical connections between teachers and learners can affect academic performance and eventually the socio-emotional skills of the learners to that effect.

Qualitative Interpretations of Results: Analysis of Interviews

To further validate the results obtained from the questionnaire used, the qualitative interpretation of data based on interviews conducted may substantiate the responses of the students and teachers/guidance advocates. This was utilized to obtain information on how they perceived and understood the content of the research. The results of the quantitative data were validated and confirmed in the encoded and decoded verbatim responses of research participants. Six themes were developed based on the participants responses. Theme 1 stated that learning process is more effective during in-person classes. Most of the answers of the student respondents indicated that learning process was more effective during in-person classes. Teachers and guidance advocates also showed their confirmation that in-person classes were more effective. Theme 2 stated that socio-emotional skills were developed more effectively during in-person classes. Teacher and guidance advocates also expressed their agreement that socio-emotional skills were developed more effectively during in-person classes. Theme 3 stated that learning is affected by socio-emotional skills. Both learners and teachers and guidance advocates affirmed that socio-emotional skills affect learners' learning. Theme 4 stated that in-person classes' dominance over other learning modalities. Likewise, some teachers and guidance advocates considered either in-person or other learning modalities. On the other hand, there were also teachers and guidance advocates who did not consider other learning modalities.

Theme 5 stated that guidance programs must focus on the development of socio-emotional skills. There were a variety of programs was suggested by students. Teachers and guidance advocates mentioned that there were

existing guidance programs in their school, but they could still suggest some. Theme 6 stated that learning strategies must focus on real-life situations. Students shared their ideas based on their experiences.

Summary and Conclusions

The summary and conclusions were drawn based on the findings of the study which were highlighted as follows: (1) Male student-respondents were lower by one (1) against the female student-respondents. Most of them were grade 12. There were more teachers than guidance advocates among the respondents/participants. Most of them was above 10 years in service, while the least was only 0-3 years in service. (2) The SHS learners' post-pandemic level of socio-emotional skills in all items under investigation was "highly competent". Learners preferred to collaboratively work with other students in completing their tasks and cooperate in class activities rather than doing their tasks alone. They also preferred acceptance of differences in beliefs, values, and sexual preferences rather than imposing theirs on others. The overall level of post-pandemic socio-emotional skills was 3.31 or "highly competent". According to them socio-emotional skills were developed more effectively during in-person classes. This could be more effective if the primary focus is on creating positive and supportive environments. (3) The post pandemic quality of learning of SHS students based on their performance during the resumption of in-person classes as assessed by students and teachers/guidance advocate respondents was "above average". Learners displayed strong motivation to learn with others. They also preferred in-person classes because it offered good results such as improved attendance in class, engagement into group activities inside and outside the classroom, increased promotion rate, decreased drop-out rate, improved grades, increased a remarkable level of interest in education, etc.

Results showed that the level of post-pandemic quality of learning of SHS learners in the Division of Binan City was 3.29 or "above average". According to them "learning process was more effective during in-person classes". (4) There was a negative linear correlation but a significant relationship between the post-pandemic social skills and the post-pandemic quality of learning of SHS students; a significant strong positive linear correlation between the post-pandemic emotional skills and the post-pandemic quality of learning; and a weak positive correlation but a significant relationship between the socio-emotional skills and the quality of learning of SHS students based on their performance during the resumption of in-person classes as perceived by teachers and students. According to them learning is affected by socio-emotional skills. It was found out that the effectiveness of physical education in the campus, including the cultivation of students' moral character, is affected by the quality of communication between teachers and students.

Based on the conclusions of the study, the following salient points are recommended for crafting programs and learning strategies: First, school guidance programs may be sustained or further improved to ensure that the level of socio-emotional skills of learners would be supported. And since in-person classes modality was preferred as the best learning modality, teachers must maximize spending quality instructional engagements among their students. Second, school instructional leaders or the principal may supervise the ways of teachers for quality assurance. Teaching strategies during in-person modality may be improved when in-person classes resumed. Real-life situations may also be considered in the delivery of every lesson to help students develop their socio-emotional skills, which perceived to be more effective in ensuring quality learning. Lastly, school programs must focus on enhancing the socio-emotional skills of the learners as it was found out that highly competent socio-emotional skills lead to above average quality of learning.

Declarations

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